

AI-DRIVEN INVENTORY OPTIMIZATION in the STAR CATEGORIZED HOTELS: BENEFITS UNVEILED

Keith Shirlvin Nigli^{*1}Dr. Anitha G^{#2}Dr. Srinivasan Pilavadisamy^{#3}Ajith Kumar Kannan^{#4}**1 Manipal Academy of Higher Education, India**#2 MKU College, India**#3 Lakshmaiah Education Foundation, India**#4 Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts and Science, India*

Abstract— *In the hospitality industry, Effective inventory management in star hotels ensures seamless operations, optimal resource utilization, and enhanced guest satisfaction by maintaining adequate stock levels of goods and services while minimizing wastage and stockouts. The star hotels face a myriad of challenges, including fluctuating demand, seasonality, and perishable inventory management. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a powerful platform to address these challenges. This article aims to depict the benefits of AI-driven inventory optimization in the star hotels by analysing the inventory turnover rate, relationship between customer satisfaction with inventory management and demand forecasting of the star hotels adopted AI driven inventory optimization (eg., Blue Yonder) in comparison with the star hotels with traditional inventory optimisation (e.g., manual tracking, spreadsheets). Through the analysis of case studies and industry trends, this article demonstrates how AI technologies can revolutionize inventory management practices in the hospitality industry. For this, both primary and secondary data have been used. In total of 200 out of 314 responses which were collected by using a self-structured questionnaire using a convenient sampling method. This research is also supported with the secondary data collected from Articles, journals, reviews and books etc.*

Keywords— Artificial Intelligence (AI), Inventory Management, Optimization, Hospitality industry, Hotel Management, Technology adoption

I. INTRODUCTION

Inventory management involves supervising and regulating the movement of goods and services within a business, ensuring the right quantities are available at the appropriate times and locations. It is also defined by [3] as a discipline tasked with maximizing resource utilization and attaining total operational efficiency among industries. Creating a meaningful and suitable inventory management policy is a difficult undertaking for many businesses [1]. Planning, acquiring, storing, and distributing inventory are some of the major duties involved. Demand forecasting, inventory level monitoring, and the application of tactics to maximize inventory turnover rates are all part of this process. Businesses may avoid stockouts, lower carrying costs, and simplify operations by keeping a close eye on inventory levels and trends.

Inventory management in star hotels involves meticulous oversight of various goods and services essential for delivering exceptional guest experiences. The hotel inventory allocation dilemma becomes more intricate due to the existence of rooms with diverse qualities, enabling hotels to either upgrade or downgrade clients' booking requests [13]. It encompasses strategic planning, procurement, storage, and distribution of items ranging from linens and toiletries to food and beverages. One method for assessing the volume of sales changes in relation to a company's average inventory over a twelve-month period is through inventory turnover [14]. The goal is to maintain optimal stock levels while minimizing excess inventory and associated costs. By leveraging advanced technologies and data analytics, hotels can forecast demand, track usage patterns, and automate replenishment processes. This ensures that guests' needs are consistently met without delays or shortages. Moreover, effective inventory control facilitates seamless coordination between different departments such as housekeeping, food and beverage, and front office, contributing to a smooth and memorable guest experience synonymous with star-rated hospitality establishments.

Traditional inventory management methods in star hotels typically involve manual processes for tracking and managing inventory. This often includes using paper-based records, spreadsheets, and manual counts to monitor stock levels, reorder supplies, and manage procurement. Under the traditional purchase order-driven approach, suppliers generate invoices upon material shipment, resulting in extended invoice-to-payment cycles, particularly when the 3-way match process [22]. Inventory replenishment decisions are often based on historical data, intuition, or periodic reviews rather than real-time insights. The inspection for quality and quantity of the orders placed will be checked almost for every order in traditional inventory optimization [10]. Additionally, storage spaces may be organized based on product categories or departments, with limited automation for inventory control. While these methods may have been sufficient in the past, they can lead to inefficiencies, inaccuracies, and increased operational costs in today's dynamic hospitality environment. Traditional inventory management methods may struggle to adapt to changing demand patterns, leading to overstocking or stockouts, which can negatively impact guest satisfaction and hotel profitability. As a result, many star hotels are increasingly turning to modern inventory management technologies to streamline operations and enhance overall efficiency.

There are two types of inventory controls namely manual inventory control and electronic inventory control. IT can establish a real-time integration of the supply chain by enabling information sharing among supply chain partners [11]. AI-driven inventory optimization in star hotels revolutionizes traditional inventory management practices by leveraging advanced algorithms and data analytics to enhance efficiency and guest satisfaction. For instance, AI algorithms can analyze historical data, booking

patterns, and seasonal trends to accurately forecast demand for various items such as linens, toiletries, and food supplies. By dynamically adjusting reorder points and quantities, AI systems ensure optimal stock levels while minimizing excess inventory and storage costs. Through mathematical modeling, [24] revealed that the efficiency of the inventory management system was heightened under Vendor-Managed Inventory (VMI), indicating the capacity to decrease traditional inventory holding expenses. Furthermore, AI-driven solutions can automate procurement processes, identifying the best suppliers and negotiating prices for bulk purchases, thereby reducing procurement expenses. Real-time monitoring and predictive analytics enable hotels to anticipate demand fluctuations and proactively manage inventory, mitigating the risk of stockouts and improving overall operational performance. Ultimately, AI-driven inventory optimization empowers star hotels to deliver seamless guest experiences while optimizing resource utilization and maximizing profitability.

The main finding of the study is that the adoption of AI-driven inventory optimization is a strategic imperative for star hotels aiming to enhance operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and profitability.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

On reviewing the literature, it is found that different authors in different periods have stated about the inventory control, management with its importance and how AI driven inventory management gives benefits in comparison with traditional inventory systems. Some of the statements are as follows

The term "inventory control systems" refers to plans and techniques that include every facet of controlling stocks, including acquisition, shipping, receiving, tracking, warehousing and storage, turnover, and reordering to satisfy client demand [2]. A strong inventory management system contributes to savings, enhanced efficiency, and reduced costs, along with various other advantages [8]. Among the main advantages of putting in place a strong inventory management program are sustained profitability, cost savings, competitive advantage, increased capacity utilization, and market diversification. [5]. Error is more likely with a manual inventory control system since it heavily depends on individual behavior [15]. Hotel profitability is pursued through a range of initiatives, among which is the focus on elevating sales growth and maintaining meticulous oversight of monthly inventory turnover [20]. According to [19], the conventional approaches of receiving reservations via mail, telephone, and facsimile are both costly and ineffective for both customers and hotels. Inventory possesses a dual nature [12]. Amazon has used analytical AI to support inventory management [21]. AI enables marketers to forecast and enhance distribution, inventory management, store displays, and layouts for both physical and online stores [6].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Design and method: For this study, employees in star hotels in different levels such as employees, managers, supervisors, partners and owners have been selected from whom the primary data responses have been collected. Using a convenient sampling method, a sample size of 200 out of 314 responses have been used for the study.

Sampling size: In total 314 responses were collected for this analysis from different employee category levels across star hotels from which 200 have been used for the analysis.

Data Collection: This study utilizes both primary and secondary data. Primary data consists of responses collected through a structured questionnaire, while secondary data is sourced from books, magazines, the internet, and newspapers to support the research.

Tools and Technologies Used: For getting primary data, Google Forms has been used. Microsoft Excel And Microsoft Power BI have been used for analysis and data visualization. Percentage analysis for exploratory data analysis and independent sample T - test for hypothesis testing have been used in this study.

Questionnaire Design: The questions were designed in a way which identifies the respondents view on the inventory optimization methods used in their organization in accordance with inventory turnover rate, forecasting methods and customer satisfaction. In total 12 questions with appropriate choices have been designed and used

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETTION

The primary data used for the research have been collected through Google forms. In total of 314 responses were collected. As the primary goal of the paper is to analyze the inventory optimisation in star hotels, the responses of the respondents who are not in the hospitality sector were removed. As the second step in data cleaning illogical responses were removed and through convenient sampling method, 200 out of 314 responses have been selected which is an equal split of respondents whose organizations were using traditional inventory optimization methods and AI driven inventory optimisation method for fair comparison. After the data cleaning process exploratory data analysis followed by count analysis for the collected data have been performed and the results are presented as below.

Among the respondents 66, 54, 42 and 38 respondents are supervisor, manager, owner and employees respectively. 72, 44, 34, 26 and 24 of the total respondents are with the experience of 6-7 years, 4-5 years, 8-10, above 10 and 1-3 years of experiences respectively. We have more responses from supervisors and respondents having 6-7 years of experience. Figure 1 and 2 gives a detailed view of how many respondent's organization implemented AI-driven inventory management systems and traditional inventory management systems in accordance with respondents' roles and experiences.

Fig. 1 Designation distribution

Periodic inventory audits are crucial for ensuring accurate stock levels, identifying discrepancies, and preventing losses. From the analysis, it is found that the inventory audits are performed every monthly irrespective of the type of inventory method they use. The above statement is supported by Fig. 3. It is also found that reordering inventory periods differ from each organization. Fig. 4 depicts the distribution of the reordering inventory periods. The reordering inventory periods are 1-2 days, 3-5 days and more than 5 days for 129, 67 and 4 respondents' organizations respectively. Forecasting the inventory demand remains a very important aspect for smooth running of an organization. Most of the respondents whose organizations using AI-driven inventory systems state that there is a higher accuracy in the inventory demand forecasting. From Fig. 5 it is found that, out of 100 employees, 88, 10 and 2 respondents stated the accuracy level as yes, unsure and no respectively.

Fig. 2 Experience distribution

Fig. 3 Inventory audit period

Fig. 4 Reordering inventory period distribution

Fig. 5 Demand forecasting accuracy distribution

Following the count analysis, hypothesis testing has been performed to test the impact of AI-driven inventory systems compared with traditional inventory systems in terms of inventory reordering time, customer satisfaction Vs inventory management and inventory forecasting. The hypothesis testing and its interpretations are stated as below. All the hypotheses were tested with the significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$). Based on the data and intention T-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means have been used for testing all the hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1 - Hypothesis testing for Inventory Reordering

Below is the hypothesis tested for finding the impact of inventory systems for inventory reordering time in star hotels.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the mean inventory reordering times between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference in the mean inventory reordering times between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

	Edible Goods		Non Edible goods	
	Traditional inventory management	AI-driven inventory management	Traditional inventory management	AI-driven inventory management
Mean	7.04	5.39	3.55	2.7
Variance	0.766060606	0.906969697	2.007575758	0.797979798
Observations	100	100	100	100
Pearson Correlation	0.005331992		0.506764998	
Mean Difference	0		0	
df	99		99	
t Stat	12.79053852		6.888233532	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.38536E-23		2.63523E-10	
t Critical one-tail	1.660391156		1.660391156	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.07707E-22		5.27045E-10	
t Critical two-tail	1.984216952		1.984216952	

Fig. 6 T - Test Output for Edible and Non-Edible Goods

Interpretation: From Fig. 6, it is found that the T - test critical value for both one - tail and two - tail tests for edible and non-edible goods are greater than the conventional significance level which are 5.3853 and 1.0770 for edible and 11.6603 and 1.9842 for non-edible goods respectively. Therefore, rejected null hypothesis. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean inventory reordering times between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

Hypothesis 2 - Hypothesis testing for Customer Satisfaction

Below is the hypothesis tested for finding the impact of inventory systems on customer satisfaction in star hotels.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the mean customer satisfaction level ratings between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference in the mean customer satisfaction level ratings between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

	Traditional inventory management methods	AI-driven inventory optimization system
Mean	3.64	4.33
Variance	0.353939394	0.405151515
Observations	100	100
Pearson Correlation	-0.056549332	
Mean Difference	0	
df	99	
t Stat	-7.705197713	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.10823E-12	
t Critical one-tail	1.660391156	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.02165E-11	
t Critical two-tail	1.984216952	

Fig. 7 T - Test Output for customer satisfaction rating

Interpretation: From Fig. 7, it is found that the T - test critical value for both one - tail and two - tail tests are greater than the conventional significance level which are 5.1082 and 1.0216 respectively. Therefore, rejected null hypothesis. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean customer satisfaction level ratings between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods.

Hypothesis 3 - Hypothesis testing for Inventory demand forecasting

Below is the hypothesis tested for finding the impact of inventory systems on demand forecasting rate in star hotels.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the mean accuracy rating of demand forecasting (μ) between hospitality establishments utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those employing traditional inventory management methods.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is no significant difference in the mean accuracy rating of demand forecasting (μ) between hospitality establishments utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those employing traditional inventory management methods.

	Traditional inventory management methods	AI-driven inventory optimization system
Mean	3.62	4.36
Variance	0.318787879	0.252929293
Observations	100	100
Pearson Correlation	-0.224818175	
Mean Difference	0	
df	99	
t Stat	-8.848523068	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.76806E-14	
t Critical one-tail	1.660391156	
P(T<=t) two-tail	3.53611E-14	
t Critical two-tail	1.984216952	

Fig. 8 T - Test Output for inventory demand forecasting rating

Interpretation: From Fig. 8, it is found that the T - test critical value for both one - tail and two - tail tests are greater than the conventional significance level which are 1.7680 and 3.536 respectively. Therefore, rejected null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean accuracy rating of demand forecasting between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those employing traditional inventory management methods.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The above analysis gives a detailed view on the impact of AI in inventory management compared with traditional inventory management. The exploratory analysis on the collected responses depicts the factors of an efficient inventory management system such as inventory audit periods, customer satisfaction and demand forecast accuracy. The analysis reveals that the inventory audit period has no much difference between the organization using AI-driven inventory management and traditional inventory management. All were doing their audits monthly. The 64.5% are mostly taking 1-2 days for reordering the inventory once it reaches certain levels followed by 33.5% of the hotels in 3 - 5 days and only fewer hotels are taking more than 5 days.

From the result of hypothesis 1, it is found that the mean values for the number of inventory reordering times are different between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods. The mean values for edible and non-edible goods are less for the hotels adopting AI-driven inventory management systems. This clearly depicts that AI is highly beneficial in reordering inventory accurately which reduces the transportation and labour charges. The accuracy in inventory reordering is also reducing the space to accumulate the inventory. From the result of hypothesis 2, it is found that the mean values for the customer satisfaction level ratings are different between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods. The mean customer satisfaction level for the star hotels adopting AI driven inventory systems are higher than those relying on traditional inventory management methods which indicates another benefit of AI in inventory management, as effective inventory management in star hotels directly impacts customer satisfaction by ensuring that guest needs are consistently met with timely and accurate availability of products and services. From the result of hypothesis 3, it is found that the mean values for the accuracy rating of demand forecasting are different between star hotels utilizing AI-driven inventory optimization systems and those relying on traditional inventory management methods. The mean accuracy rating of demand forecasting for the star hotels adopting AI driven inventory systems are higher than those relying on traditional inventory management methods. The discrepancy arises because AI algorithms

can scrutinize historical data, trends in the market, and factors to produce more precise demand forecasts. This allows businesses to fine-tune inventory levels, avoid stockouts, and cut down on excess inventory holding costs.

The other hidden benefits identified are dynamic pricing strategies and improved operational efficiency. AI-powered pricing algorithms can dynamically adjust prices based on real-time demand fluctuations, competitor pricing, and other market dynamics. This allows businesses to maximize revenue by offering optimal pricing strategies tailored to specific market conditions. AI-driven inventory optimization automates repetitive tasks such as inventory replenishment, order management, and procurement, freeing up staff to focus on more strategic activities. This leads to improved operational efficiency and cost savings. The prevailing literature also suggests that the implementation of sophisticated and complex inventory models can improve performance. Nonetheless, superior performance is achieved through a fusion of basic inventory theory and uncomplicated management procedures executed by seasoned personnel [4].

Even though AI-driven inventory optimization has a lot of potential for the hospitality industry, there are still a few obstacles to overcome. These include issues with data privacy, system integration, and the requirement for qualified workers to decipher insights produced by AI. The hospitality business has great prospects to improve inventory management procedures through the integration of prescriptive recommendations and predictive analytics, which is one of the current breakthroughs in AI technology.

VI. CONCLUSION

The transformational potential of AI-driven inventory optimization in star-categorized hotels is emphasized in this study. It is clear from comparing AI-driven systems with traditional inventory management techniques that AI greatly improves customer happiness, demand forecasting accuracy, and inventory turnover rates. AI-driven solutions streamline reordering processes, reduce operational costs, and ensure timely availability of products and services, thereby improving overall guest experience and hotel profitability. The findings demonstrate that hotels adopting AI-driven inventory management systems can achieve more accurate demand forecasts, enhanced efficiency in inventory management contributes to higher customer satisfaction levels, as guests' needs are met more consistently and promptly. Despite the promising benefits, challenges such as data privacy concerns, system integration issues, and the need for skilled personnel remain. However, with the ongoing advancements in AI technology, these obstacles can be addressed, paving the way for even more sophisticated and effective inventory management solutions. Walmart has begun testing autonomous robots in some stores to scan shelves for items that need restocking [10].

In conclusion, adopting AI-driven inventory optimization is a strategic necessity for star hotels seeking to improve operational efficiency, client satisfaction, and profitability. Integrating AI technologies into inventory management not only resolves the traditional challenges of the hospitality industry but also paves the way for innovation and growth.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to extend their heartfelt thanks to everyone who contributed to the completion of this article.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors confirm no conflicts of interest. They have all approved the final version of the manuscript and have contributed equally to its creation

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